

IDENTIFICATION OF DENGUE HAEMORRHAGIC FEVER (DHF) OCCURRENCE PROBABILITY BASED ON CLIMATE PARAMETER AND ITS PROJECTION CASE STUDY: EAST JAVA

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Abstract

The change of global average temperature as the impact of global warming has taken big attention among people nowadays. anthropogenic factors which derived from human activities have increased the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere so it might change the climate parameters such as rainfall pattern and the rate of temperature. The changes in these environmental components will affect species in ecosystem groups, vector patterns, and disease viruses. Dengue Haemorrhagic Fever (DHF) is a disease that caused by the virus and transmitted through *Aedes Aegypti* mosquito. A recent study showed that 80% DHF risk occurrence could be explained by those climate parameters. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between the events of DHF cases and climate parameter in East Java as one of the endemic places of DHF in Indonesia and also to project the probability of DHF occurrence period of 2020-2050 based on Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP 4.5). Statistical methods including principal component analysis, downscaling, correlation, and ordinal logistic regression was carried out. The results showed that probability of DHF occurrence was high during peak rain season (DJF) and gradually weakened as went to dry season. The projection for 2020-2050 period didn't show a significant change in general compared to present but some area increased and decreased sharply.

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1. Introduction

Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has released the fourth assessment report showing a variety of scientific evidence about the contribution of human activities (anthropogenic factors) in increasing the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere that accelerates the rate of global temperature increase that causes climate change. It was reported that for the current 100 years (1906-2005), the global average temperature increased to $0.74^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.18^{\circ}\text{C}$ [1]. Climate change is projected to impact the sustainable development in developing countries in Asia because it combines pressure on natural resources and the environment related to urbanization, industrialization and rapid economic development [2].

The projection of the trend of economic activity and the impact of gas emissions on human activities, in the coming year, seems to influence the shift on rainfall patterns and the average temperature of the earth which is estimated to be increased by 1–3.5°C. The changes in these environmental components will affect species in ecosystem groups. As a heterogeneous tropical country, Indonesia is vulnerable to the impacts of regional and global climate change. Macro

and microclimate changes can affect the spread of infectious diseases, including mosquito vectors (*Culex Modestus*). The increase of humidity and rainfall are in line with the increase of mosquito density, while the optimum temperature for mosquito breeding ranges between 25-27°C [4].

Dengue Haemorrhagic Fever (DHF) is an infectious disease that caused by the virus and transmitted through mosquitoes. It has become one of the public health problems in Indonesia which tend to be increasingly widespread in line with mobility and population density increase. Most cases of dengue fever are reported in a high populated area such as provinces in Java, Bali and Sumatra [5]. Java Island as the most populous island in Indonesia is estimated to reach around 150 million in 2015 from around 250 million Indonesian population in total [6].

IPCC has compiled various greenhouse gas emission scenarios where the latest emission scenario is Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP). It describes four possible climate futures, all of which are considered possible depending on how much greenhouse gases are emitted in the years to come. The four scenarios are named after a possible range of radiative forcing value in the year of 2100 namely RCP2.6, RCP4.5, RCP6.0, and RCP8.5. This research identified how the relationship between climate elements and dengue cases and how the projections of future dengue occurrence probability based on RCP 4.5 during the period of 2020-2050, in order to get an overview about future planning of adaptation and mitigation measures towards this issue.

2. Data and Method

This study uses monthly average temperature (T) and monthly rainfall (CH) data period of 1992-2010 obtained from 10 Meteorological stations in East Java. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used to simplify the climate data from 10 stations in Java province into one variable. It is a multivariate analysis that transforms many variables into smaller dimensions but it can still explain the variability of whole variables. The data of dengue case occurrences during the same period collected from East Java Provincial Health Office were used as well. The DHF occurrences are divided into 3 categories based on data percentile which consist of low (below the 30th percentile), medium (30th-70th percentile), and high (above the 70th percentile). Meanwhile, the RCP 4.5 data were obtained from Australia's Commonwealth of Industrial and Scientific Research Organizations (CSIRO) during the period of 2020-2050. A statistical downscaling method was used to generate a statistical model that show the functional relationships between predictor variables and local response variables. This method was used to obtain projection data in RCP 4.5 to be downsized in the study are which focused in East Java Province. Ordinal Logistic Regression Model (OLRM) calculates the DHF occurrence probability projection based on projected rainfall and temperature during the period of 2020-2050.

3. Result

3.1 Temperature

The Projection of air temperature for the period of 2020-2050 (Figure 1.b) generally shows an increase compared to the baseline period (Figure 1.a) where the highest temperature occurred from October to December. It caused by the pseudo-motion of the sun where from October to December, the sun will move towards the south of the equator and the position of East Java

region is southern from the equator so the solar energy will receive greater energy rather than other months, and the air temperature will be lower from June to August because the sun is far north from equator.

According to the temperature difference between the baseline and projected period (Figure 1.c), Temperature tends to increase in all months which means that East Java will be warmer in the next 30 years. The areas that have the highest differences include Perak I, Perak II and Juanda where the highest difference occurs in October to December reaching about 1.3°C even more. these three stations are located in one administrative area called The Capital City of Surabaya where they have similar geographical conditions such as located near the sea, in highly populated areas and running large industries.

FIGURE 1. Monthly average temperature during a. Baseline period (1992-2010) b. Projected period (2020-2050) c. Temperature difference between projected and baseline period

Spatially, Figure 2 shows that temperature in East Java region varies in location that is relatively large due to the geographical conditions of East Java which are quite different where the central part of East Java like Tretes and Karangates stations are located in highland so the temperature will colder meanwhile the northern part of East Java like Juanda, Perak I and Perak II and eastern part of East Java like Banyuwangi are located in lowland and tend to be hotter because these regions are urban areas.

FIGURE 2. PROJECTION OF FUTURE TEMPERATURE PERIOD OF 2020-2050 BASED ON RCP 4.5 SCENARIO

3.2 Rainfall

The results of the rainfall projection period of 2020-2050 (Figure 3.b) shows a similar pattern compared to the baseline period (Figure 3.a) where it has unimodal patterns (one peak of the rainy season). The dry season occurs during June-August and the rainy season occurs during

December-February. Meanwhile, the rest are categorised into transition season. The areas that are affected by the monsoon pattern is in the southern part of Sumatra, Central and South Kalimantan, Java, Bali, Nusa Tenggara and some of Papua [9]. With the existence of rainfall patterns such that monsoon based on baseline period, projection data this shows that future projections for rainfall will not have a significant effect.

According to rainfall difference between the projection and baseline period (Figure 3.c), most of the regions fluctuate the rainfall significantly where some are lesser than current and some are more than 200 mm. In the months that are projected forward have high rainfall needs to be watched because increasing rainfall volume will increase the potential increase in the influence of the development of *Aedes Aegypti* mosquitoes through the puddles generated after rain.

FIGURE 3. Monthly Average Rainfall During A. Baseline Period (1992-2010) B. Projected Period (2020-2050) C. Rainfall Difference Between Projected And Baseline Period

FIGURE 4 Projection Of Future Rainfall Period Of 2020-2050 Based On Rcp 4.5 Scenario

Based on the difference in projection data and baseline data in Figure 7, almost in various regions have a very fluctuating difference, where there is rainfall that is smaller than the current rainfall and there is a larger up to 200 mm. In the months that are projected forward have high rainfall needs to be watched because increasing rainfall volume will increase the potential increase in the influence of the development of *Aedes Aegypti* mosquitoes through the puddles generated after rain.

Spatially in Figure 8, shows that the East Java region has a uniform rainfall distribution pattern where in January to March has high rainfall ranging from 200-400 mm, which high rainfall will be very influential with the development of dengue cases.

3.3. DHF

Figure 5. Monthly DHF Case Occurrence in East Java During Baseline Period (1992-2010)

Figure 6. Projection of DHF Occurrence Probability in the Future (Period of 2021-2050)

From the incidence case data of dengue in East Java province period 1992-2010, the highest incidence of dengue occurred in January to March, for the results of the projected probability of occurrence based on 3 categories of low, medium and high, the value of potential opportunities in each category as follows:

By using the logistic model, the projection value in Figure 10. show the low DHF incident risk classification has probability value ranges from 0.08-0.67, the risk of medium/moderate DHF incident classification ranges from 0.31 to 0.47 and the risk of high DHF incident classification ranges from 0.06-0.61. Based on the comparison of opportunity values in the three categories, the chance of dengue risk in the East Java region is very volatile following the rainfall pattern where in January and February during high rainfall the opportunity value of high category DHF incident is above 0.5 or 50%, while in July to October when the rainfall is low or during the dry season the chance of DHF in the low category is above 0.5, but in general the East Java region has a moderate risk of DHF according to a report in the epidemiological window of the Indonesian Ministry of Health in 2010.10 Projection of DHF cases also shows that in the future Java region East is still classified as an area with medium/moderate risk of dengue.

Based on the results described above, there are several things that need to be considered and understood together regarding the purpose of writing in this paper, that human activities will encourage the rapid climate change that occurs, increasing population, reduced land and forest

functions for settlements will cause bad impact like rising air temperature due to carbon gases trapped in the atmosphere. In the health sector, that is DHF, an increase of air temperature will accelerate the population of *Aedes Aegypti* mosquitoes. Relatively warm air conditions range from 26-30°C is suitable with the life cycle and development of *Aedes Aegypti* mosquito[11]. Furthermore, for the results of the projected rainfall in the period 2020-2050, the rainfall pattern is still the same as the current rainfall pattern, but the volume of rainfall shows a significant increase and decrease in certain months, the increase occurred mainly in January to March, where these months will usually occur with the peak of the rainy season in areas with monsoonal rain types. An increase in air temperature also occurred in several regions with a considerable difference in the months of October to December.

Projection of the potential opportunities for DHF shows that the chances of dengue cases with high potential occur in the months of January to March, because these months in the East Java region have high rainfall, this will cause mosquito larvae to develop quickly if exposed to water and warm temperatures, the role of both as environmental providers and triggers of mosquito breeding is quite influential. Although in general, the projection of the potential opportunities for dengue fever in East Java is still relatively moderate, it is better if preventive measures are taken to anticipate dengue fever outbreaks when the rainy season arrives, such as cleaning up garbage, closing water reservoirs, fogging, etc. This is well done in order to minimize the case of DHF that will occur

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion, the conclusion in this study is that the average monthly temperature projection for the period 2020-2050 in the East Java region has increased, especially in October to December. While the projection of monthly average rainfall for the period 2020-2050 in the East Java region in general the rainfall pattern does not have significant changes, but there are areas that have increased and decreased the volume of rainfall where it can increase the development potential of *Aedes Aegypti* mosquitoes. Meanwhile, for the projection of potential opportunities for dengue cases in the period 2020-2050 in the East Java region generally shows that the potential opportunities are classified as medium dengue risk.

5. Suggestion

Climate change caused by anthropogenic factors from human activities can cause diseases that are harmful to humans so mitigation measures are needed to reduce the impact through programs and policies from the government and relevant agencies so as to reduce the rate of climate change.

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